

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING FILMS CONTAINING ANTI EMETIC DRUG

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ABSTRACT

Oral route is considered as one of the most convenient routes for administration of various pharmaceutical dosage forms like, tablet, capsule, syrup, suspension and emulsion. Fast Dissolving Drug Delivery systems have developed various fast disintegrating preparations like mouth dissolving film, MDT. Oral thin film are new dosage form that are prepared from hydrophilic polymer which are when placed in mouth, buccal cavity disintegrates rapidly. Mouth dissolving film is superior as compare to mouth dissolving tablets as the cost of production is low. Geriatric and paediatric patients are facing difficulty in swallowing of tablet and capsule, the oral film can bypass it, along with that it has other advantages like self-administrable, fast dissolving, rapid absorption that make it versatile dosage form. The aim of present study is to enlighten specifically

different polymer along with their concentrations and applications. This study also focuses on use of plasticizer, polymer, sweetener, different methods.

INTRODUCTION

Fast dissolving oral film (FDOF) is defined as “an ultra-thin film containing active ingredient that dissolves or disintegrates in the saliva at a remarkably fast rate, within few seconds without the aid of water or chewing”. Fast dissolving oral films (FDOFs) are the most advanced form of oral solid dosage form due to more flexibility and comfort. It improves the efficacy of APIs by dissolving within minute in oral cavity after the contact with saliva

without chewing and no need of water for administration. It gives quick absorption and instant bioavailability of drugs due to high blood flow and permeability of oral mucosa is 4-1000 times greater than that of skin.^[1] FDOFs are Oral route is most preferred route by medical practitioners and manufacturer due to highest acceptability of patients. About 60% of all dosage forms available are the oral solid dosage form. The lower bioavailability, long onset time and dysphagia patients turned the manufacturer to the Parenterals and liquid useful in patients such as paediatric, geriatrics, bedridden, emetic patients, diarrhoea, sudden episode of allergic attacks, or coughing FDOFs are prepared using hydrophilic polymer that rapidly dissolves on the buccal cavity, delivering the drug to the systemic circulation via buccal mucosa.^[2,3,4]

Advantages of Oral FDFs

- ✓ ODFs can be administered without water, anywhere & anytime.
- ✓ Larger superficial area (LSA) films aid in rapid disintegration as well as in dissolution of the bodies oral cavity.
- ✓ Promoting mouth-freshening property^[5]

Disadvantages

- ✓ Drugs that are required in high doses made difficult formulate into thin films. For instance, Rifampin (600mg), Ethambutol(1000mg).^[6]
- ✓ Thermal process of drying affect drug & polymer stability.
- ✓ Require packing(special) for products stability & safety

Antiemetic Drugs

Emetic means a medicine or other substance which causes vomiting. Emetic is medicine or portion that makes person to vomit, which might be given if person has taken poison or some other harmful substance. Also used for morning sickness, but there is little information about the effect on the foetus.^[7,8]

The need of the present work is to develop Fast Dissolving Oral Films of Granisetron. Granisetron Hydrochloride is an orally active 5-HT₃ receptor antagonist treats the chemotherapy induced nausea and vomiting (CINV) and postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV). It is water-soluble drug has bitter taste. Because of patient may have trouble in swallowing a tablet or capsules. Also, CINV is a sever condition requires quick relief. FDOFs totally serve this purpose hence, FDOF of Granisetron HCl is required. In order to assist

patients during travelling, where water may not be always available and in dysphasia patients (those who have difficulty in swallowing), there is necessity for the development of these fast-dissolving systems. Granisetron Hydrochloride administered by this route is rapidly absorbed and avoids first pass metabolism, thereby increasing the bioavailability. These dosage forms are designed in such a way that they dissolve or disintegrate in patients mouth up on contact with saliva, within seconds without aid of water.

The main objective of the present study outlines a systematic approach for Design and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Oral Films of Granisetron Hydrochloride to enhance the therapeutic efficacy and provide rapid onset of action in patients suffering from Emetic.

Drug Profile

IUPAC-NAME: 1-methyl-N-((1R, 3r, 5S)-9-methyl-9-azabicyclo [3.3.1] nonan-3-yl)-1H-indazole-3-carboxamide

Empirical Formula: C₁₈H₂₄N₄O.HCL

Molecular Weight: 348.9(312.4 free base)

Melting Range: 219°C

Category: Antiemetic

Colour: White to off-white

Solubility: Readily soluble in water and normal saline at 20°C.

Taste: Bitter

Nature: Crystalline powder

Half-life: 3-14 hours Bioavailability:

Absolute Bio Availability 60% 27

Distribution: Plasma Protein Binding 65%

Metabolism: Hepatic, mediated by cytochrome P-450 3A

Excretion: 48% in urine & 38% in feces Adverse effects: Headache, Constipation, Asthenia, Diarrhoea, Abdominal pain, Dyspepsia Dose & administration: 2mg once daily or 1mg twice

daily for oral administration.

Mechanism of Action: Granisetron is a selective 5- hydroxytryptamine₃ (5-HT₃) receptor antagonist with little or no affinity for other serotonin receptors, including 5-HT₁; 5-HT_{1A}; 5-HT_{1B/C};5-HT₂; for alpha₁.alpha₂., or beta-adreno receptors; for dopamine-D₂; or for histamine-H₁; benzodiazepine; picrotoxin or opioid receptors.^[9,10]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pre-formulation studies

Pre-formulation study helps a formulation scientist develop safe, effective dosage forms, at a large scale for a drug under study.

Preparation of standardization curve

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer (pH 6.8): This buffer was prepared by mixing.

Table 01: Preparation of Phosphate Buffer.

250ml 0.2M potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH ₂ PO ₄) solution	250ml 0.2M potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH ₂ PO ₄) solution
112ml 0.2M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution	112ml 0.2M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution
Then make up-to 1L using purified water.	

Preparation of standard solution of Granisetron Hydrochloride

1mg of Granisetron Hydrochloride was weighed accurately in a digital weighing balance and transferred into a dry 100ml volumetric flask. 10ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was added and the drug was dissolved. The volume was then made up to 100ml using phosphate buffer pH6.8. This solution was considered as stock solution whose concentration was 10µg/ml or 10ppm. From 10ppm solution, solutions of 1ml, 2ml, 4ml, 6ml, 8ml, and 10ml were transferred into 10ml volumetric flasks and their volume was made up to 10ml. The concentrations of these solutions are 1ppm, 2ppm, 4ppm, 6ppm, 8ppm and 10ppm. These solutions were used to plot standard calibration curve.

Calibration Curve

Calibration curve obtaining method of Granisetron HCl was carried out by scanning 100ppm solution from 400 to 200nm in spectrum (mode) of UV-Visible spectrophotometer. From this spectrum absorbance maximum was selected. Solutions absorbance from 1ppm to 10ppm and 10ppm to 20ppm was measured in a Shimadzu double beam UV-spectrophotometer, in

photometric mode, using pH 6.8 (phosphate buffer) as a reference blank. Absorbance maxima was obtained by the procedure that was carried and from that the spectrum was formed.

Table 02: Formulation using HPMC.

FORMULATION CODE & INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4
GRANISETRON HYDROCHLORIDE (mg)	17.92	17.92	17.92	17.92
HPMC (mg)	225	250	275	300
MALTODEXTRIN (mg)	130	120	110	100
XANTHAN GUM (mg)	10	10	8	8
ASPARTAME (mg)	20	20	20	20
AMARANTH	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S
PROPYLENE GLYCOL	50	60	70	80
CITRIC ACID (mg)	10	10	10	10
WATER	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S
VANILLA	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S

Figure 01: Granisetron HCl fil.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Calibration curve of Granisetron Hydrochlorid Absorption spectrum of Granisetron-Hydrochloride λ_{max} was found to be 302 nm in SHIMADZUUV-1800.

Graph 01: UV Spectrum of Granisetron Hydrochloride (210µG/ML).

Table 03: Standard graph of Granisetron Hydrochloride.

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance(308nm)
0	0
2	0.144
4	0.280
6	0.423
8	0.560
10	0.679

Graph 02: Standard Graph of Granisetron Hydrochloride (1- 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) Preliminary characterization of FDOFs.

Physical characterization of FDOFs was carried out by visual inspection and the following was observed.

- ✓ The films were evenly coloured and no migration of colour was observed.
- ✓ F1 to F3 films with more HPMC were found to be thick.
- ✓ F1 to F3 were found to be brittle in nature and difficult to peel whereas others separated easily.
- ✓ Increased opacity and decreased transparency is due to increase in the amount of maltodextrin proportionately to HPMC.
- ✓ The films obtained from all the formulations had smooth surface on either side.

ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES

Table 04: Organoleptic Properties Property.

S. No	Parameter
1	White in color
2	Characteristics in odor
3	Bitter in Taste
4	Melting Point:

Table 05: Preliminary characterization of FDOF.

Code & property	Film Property	Tack Property	Ease of handling
F1	Good	Non- Tacky	Opaque, Easy to peel
F2	Excellent	Non- Tacky	Thin, Peeling makes easy
F3	Excellent	Non- Tacky	Thin, Easy to peel
F4	Good	Non- Tacky	Soft, easy to peel

Invitro quality control tests**Table 06: In Vitro quality control tests (mean SD n = 3).**

Code	Thickness	Weight variation(mg)	Folding Endurance(count)	Surface ph	Content Uniformity (%)	In vitro Disintegration Time
F1	88 ± 0	82.1 ± 04	86 ± 5	6.67 ± 0.01	92.2 ± 06	18 ± 2
F2	85 ± 2	80.2 ± 0.3	90 ± 2	6.93 ± 0.02	97.6 ± 2.2	15 ± 2
F3	87 ± 1	84.3±0.1	96±1	6.94.3±0.01	98.6±0.55	14±2
F4	88 ± 1	86.0 ± 0.3	98 ± 1	6.89± 0.03	97.7 ± 0.45	18 ± 2

The present invention identifies that the HPMC grades is one of the best water-soluble polymer and best used for the preparation of fast.

Tensile Strength & Percent Elongation

Tensile strength test was performed for selected formulations that are more like optimized formulation.

Table 07: Tensile Strength & Percent Elongation.

FORMULATION CODE	TENSILE STRENGTH(g/cm ²)	PERCENT ELONGATION (%)
F1	11.6±0.27	9.8±0.21
F2	9.6±0.91	8.2±0.16
F3	9.7±0.19	8.1±0.71
F4	10.7±0.31	9.3±0.50

Invitro Dissolution studies**Table 08: Invitro Dissolution studies.**

FORMULATION CODE TIME(MINUTES)	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	12.3±1.2	17.8±2.4	23.3±1.1	25.5±2.4
2	22.9±1.0	28.3±1.2	38.9±3.4	40.8±1.0
4	40.2±2.2	42.3±1.0	55.6±1.0	60.6±1.7
6	56.9±1.3	58.7±2.4	67.7±2.3	82.3±1.5
8	73.8±1.2	72.5±1.0	85.2±2.2	90.1±1.1
10	80.2±2.2	82.3±1.6	90.2±2.2	90.1±1.0

Graph 03: Cumulative Percent Drug Release.

Drug excipient interactions studies by FTIR Spectroscopy`

Graph 04: FTIR Spectroscopy of Granisetron Hydrochloride Formulation.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Fast dissolving Oral film of was formulated by using solvent casting method with different concentrations. Film forming property of various grades of HPMC was investigated based on preliminary characteristics of various batches of FDOFs. Formulations were not evaluated for other physical parameters due to their poor film forming ability, tack property and ease of handling or peeling.

The bitter taste of the drug was masked by Aspartame and Vanilla flavour. Formulations were evaluated for their physical characteristics, thickness, folding endurance, tensile strength, disintegration time, drug content uniformity and drug release characteristics.

Dissolution studies were performed for FDOFs excluding batches that showed poor film forming property.

Among the prepared formulations F3 showed minimum disintegration time 12 sec. Formulation F3 released 97.8% of drug within 8 min when compared to the other formulations. Based on the physicochemical properties like tensile strength, folding endurance, thickness, disintegration results and dissolution studies, it was concluded that F3 finalized as optimized formulation.

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